

Application form Open Science Meetings

Do not adjust or delete any parts of this form. If you have any questions contact us.

1 Overview

1.1 Applicant details

1.1.1 Main applicant details

Title of the proposal*:	Developing a Diamond Open Access Discovery Kit
Applicant name: Title(s), initial(s), (prefix,) surname(s)	C. Livio
E-mail:	c.livio@uu.nl
Telephone number:	██████████
Affiliation:	Utrecht University
Faculty/Department:	Utrecht University Library, Publishing Support Department
Type of position:	Open Access Advisor

* This title should be the same as the title you enter in ISAAC.

1.1.2 Co-applicant details

You cannot add more than one co-applicant.

Applicant name: Title(s), initial(s), (prefix,) surname(s)	A. van den Maagdenberg
E-mail:	a.vanden.maagdenberg@vu.nl
Telephone number:	██████████
Affiliation:	Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam
Faculty/Department:	Universiteitsbibliotheek
Type of position:	Open Access Librarian

2 Project description

2.1 Meeting details

Name of the meeting:	Developing a Diamond Open Access Discovery Kit
Location (city/venue):	Utrecht, SURF
Date (first day):	28-5-2025
Date (last day):	28-5-2025
Type of meeting:	National Scientific Meeting
Website (optional)*:	<i>The event will be promoted on openaccess.nl as well as OS-NL Open Science Community websites. In addition, each University library will be asked to share the event via their official channels. Registration form will be created on openaccess.nl in collaboration with the Diamond OA Expertise Centre.</i>

** If no event website exists, leave empty. If a website is made available after submission of this form, please inform us on opensciencemeetings@nwo.nl*

2.2 Relevance to Open Science

Indicate how your proposal relates to Open Science in your field or more broadly (do not exceed the maximum of 100 words).

Relevance to Open Science:	When practising Open Science, researchers publishing their work Open Access have a diverse range of models and journals to consider. Awareness of the different options is not always present, and consequences of choices are not straightforward. To date, most of the attention and support researchers receive from university libraries is focused on traditional for-profit scholarly outlets. Libraries need to be able to advise researchers on more suitable, inclusive, and equitable publishing models such as Diamond Open Access. By hosting this meeting, we will ensure that libraries feel empowered to discuss viable Diamond Open Access alternatives with their researchers.
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2.3 Meeting description

Please describe the context, goal and (inter)national importance for Open Science of the proposed meeting (do not exceed the maximum of 200 words per item).

2.3.1 Context

The current publication landscape is increasingly in need of reform. As long as scholarly communication is left in the hands of for-profit publishers, sustainable, equitable, and inclusive open access will remain unattainable. In this scenario, open access is mostly limited to countries that have sufficient infrastructure and funding to engage in transformative agreements, cover the costs of open access publication fees (APCs), or support their researchers with green open-access alternatives. However, research communities in South America and Africa are showing that a more inclusive and equitable approach to open access is possible: Diamond Open Access (Diamond OA). Despite its apparent benefits and current national trends (see, for instance, the [NWO Diamond Open Access Fund](#)), the uptake of Diamond OA is still minimal with only 3-4% of short scientific works being published in Diamond OA outlets in the Netherlands (See Bosman, J., Frantsvåg, J. E., Kramer, B., Langlais, P.-C., & Proudman, V. (2021). OA Diamond Journals Study. Part 1: Findings. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4558704>). In this context, librarians play a key role in supporting researchers with their publication strategy, making them an important target group to educate and update on Diamond OA options and developments.

word count: 192 (max. 200)

2.3.2 Goal

Many researchers are often unaware of the Diamond OA model and the variety of journals that could serve as attractive publication venues for their work. Librarians play a pivotal role in raising awareness about the publication routes available to researchers. However, not all librarians possess the same level of expertise in the Diamond OA landscape and may not all be equipped to effectively communicate and advise on this topic. The goal of this session is for librarians and researchers to co-create and develop a “Diamond OA Discovery Kit” that librarians (but also faculty liaisons, policy advisors, and research support officers) can adapt and use to promote awareness of Diamond OA options at the local level. Through this session, we also aim to establish a national framework for the support that librarians can offer in relation to Diamond OA.

word count: 138 (max. 200)

2.3.3 (Inter)national importance for Open Science

Raising awareness of Diamond OA, particularly its initiatives, is a crucial first step toward creating a more equitable and inclusive publishing landscape. When researchers are unaware of alternatives to traditional for-profit publishing models, they cannot make informed decisions or explore different options. By promoting awareness of Diamond OA at the national level, we can optimize resources and build momentum for meaningful change. To facilitate adaptation and reuse at both national and international levels, all materials developed during and after this session will be published online under a CC BY license.

word count: 90 (max. 200)

3 Programme

Describe the (provisional) programme of the meeting. (You may replace the text field below with a table or image)

The program outlined below is preliminary and subject to change.

10:00-10:30 – **Opening – 2 speakers**

10:30-12:00 – **Conversation: Researchers Needs and Wants – 3 speakers, 1 moderator**
(Panel Discussion)

- What do researchers prioritize in a journal?
- How do researchers navigate the search for the right journal?

12:00-13:00 – **Lunch break**

13:00-14:30 – **Hands-on: Designing the *Diamond OA Discovery Kit***

- Integrating researchers' perspectives and needs
- Elements for an effective *Diamond OA Discovery Kit*

14:30-15:00 – **Coffee break**

15:00-16:30 – **Engagement: Strategies for impact**

- Capturing researchers' attention with the Discovery Kit
- Adapting the kit for maximum outreach to researchers

16:30-17:00 – **Final remarks and drinks**

Max. 2 pages (attachments are not allowed)

4 Participants

The meeting must be open to all possible participants in the Netherlands.

4.1 Number of expected participants

Indicate the total number of expected participants.

Number of participants from Dutch universities/universities of applied sciences/institutes/organisations/partners:	50
Number of participants from international universities/universities of applied sciences/institutes/organisations/partners:	10
Total number of participants:	60

4.2 Distribution of participants

Indicate how many participants are expected from which universities/universities of applied sciences/institutes/organisations/partners. In the case of international participants, include at least the countries. Meetings are expected to have a diverse audience, meetings where all participants exclusively represent the applicant's organization, will not be funded.

We expect about 60 participants, with a spread over university and universities of applied sciences in the Netherlands (e.g., Librarians, Researchers, OA experts, Data Stewards, Policy advisors, Faculty staff, etc.).

4.3 Distribution of speakers

Indicate how many speakers are expected from which universities/universities of applied sciences/institutes/organisations/partners. In the case of international speakers, include at least the countries.

We expect the following 4 guest speakers and co-organizers:

1. Anna van 't Veer – researcher (Universiteit Leiden)
2. Bregt Lameris – researcher (Open Universiteit)
3. Maria Constantin – open access officer (Erasmus University Rotterdam)
4. Anne van den Maagdenberg – open access librarian (Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam)

5 Budget

5.1 Project Expenses and Revenues

5.1.1 Expenses

Please fill in one of the columns in the table below.

(Please note that not all items are eligible for funding).

	Budget
Eligible expenses:	
Costs for digital platform*	€ 1,000 (for workshop materials, stickers, etc.)
Costs renting location + facilities	€ 2,000 (for professional design of the finalized Diamond OA Discovery Kit)
Accommodation costs (coffee/tea/ lunch/ dinner / reception / overnight stay)	€ 2,500 for 60 participants (we do not plan to reimburse overnight stays)
Travel and accommodation costs guest speakers(s)	€ 500 (for travel reimbursement of guest speakers)
Costs child care (on site)	€
Costs for making the meeting accessible for participants with disabilities	€
Total eligible expenses:	€ 6,000
Non-eligible expenses:	
Other attendance costs participants	€
Costs organisation/professional congress organiser	€
Other costs	€
Total non-eligible expenses:	€
Total (eligible + non-eligible) expenditure	€

5.1.2 Revenues

You may add rows to the table below to present the revenues.

<Name contributing party>	€
<Name contributing party>	€
<Name contributing party>	€
Registration fees participants*	€ 0 (the event is free of charge)
Other revenues	€
Total revenues	€

**If applicable: indicate the total expected amount in fees*

5.1.3 Budget

Please note the maximum remuneration is € 100 per eligible participant, with a maximum of € 15.000,- for meetings.

Contribution requested:	€ 6,000
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Are the total revenues (5.1.2) and contribution from Open Science NL (5.1.3) equal to the total expenditure (5.1.1)? If no, explain below.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no

5.2 Additional funding from NWO / Open Science NL

Have you applied, or will you apply, for any additional funding from NWO / Open Science NL for this meeting?

yes/no (If yes, please provide details).

no

Is NWO / Open Science NL contributing in any other way to this meeting, e.g. by offering a location or funding through another programme, such as a personal grant, or an NWA or KIC programme?

yes/no (If yes, please provide details).

no

6 Additional questions

6.1 Promotion of the meeting

How will you promote the meeting?

The event will be promoted on openaccess.nl, Open Science Community websites and asked to be disseminated by each University library as well as social media. Registration form will be hosted on openaccess.nl in collaboration with the Diamond OA Expertise Centre (national program: "Strengthening Diamond Open Access in the Netherlands").

6.2 How will you publicise the funding awarded by Open Science NL?

If Open Science NL awards funding, then Open Science NL expects an acknowledgement of the financial support, for example through the placement of the Open Science NL logo on the programme or through an announcement.

How will you publicise the funding awarded by Open Science NL?

Open Science NL will be acknowledged during the promotion of the event (see above) and in each deliverable that will derive from the meeting.

7 Statements by the main applicant

By submitting this form I declare that:

Please check the boxes to confirm.

- By submitting this application form, I declare that I am appointed at my host institute until after the meeting that is applied for has taken place.
- By submitting this application form, I declare that I and all individuals involved in this proposal satisfy the nationally and internationally accepted standards for scientific conduct as stated in the *Netherlands Code of Conduct for Scientific Practice 2014* (Association of Universities in the Netherlands)
- By submitting this application form, I declare that I have discussed the final version of this proposal with all individuals involved in the organization of this meeting. All such individuals are aware of and agree with the content of this application.
- By submitting this application form, I declare I have taken notice of the rules for this call for proposals.
- By submitting this application form, I declare that I have completed this application form truthfully.

Name: Chiara Livio

Place: Utrecht University Library, Utrecht

Date: 03/12/2024

Before you submit the proposal in ISAAC you will be asked to confirm again that you have completed the form truthfully.

Please submit the application to Open Science NL (pdf format is required!) via the online application system ISAAC, which can be accessed via the Open Science NL and NWO website. The application must be submitted from the account of the main applicant. For any technical questions regarding submission, please contact the ISAAC helpdesk (isaac.helpdesk@nwo.nl).